

PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF DYSPHEMISMS IN FRENCH

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Annotation: This article will talk about the concept of dysphemism, the feedback of linguistic scholars on this concept, the pragmatic features of dysphemisms in the French language. It has also been suggested that the phenomenon of dysphemism, its characteristic feature, dysphemism is a discursive phenomenon, and dysphemism is both a linguistic and a speech phenomenon.

Keywords: dysphemism, euphemism, dysphemism, cacophenism, orthophenism.

Each language has bypassed words that are either optional or non-optional. Most of them are words that are considered “unpleasant”, “offensive” by the speaker, the rest of the audience. Today, the number of words that express a negative meaning in themselves is growing. This leads to the need to study the essence of the concept, the reasons for its appearance, which in linguistics is called “dysphemism”. There are several reasons for speech rudeness. Sociologists and sociolinguists note that “deepening stratification between social groups in different areas of life, conflict of interest, the existence of one group’s desire to dominate another group” led to a roughening of speech [Kvaskova, 2016:353].

Today, there is no complete and absolute theory about the general Laws of the formation and application of dysphemisms. Linguistic scientist A.N.Rezanova explains the reason for the in-depth lack of study of dysphemisms as “a concept contrary to moral norms”. Despite the fact that dysphemisms are common in oral speech, their use in literary speech is prohibited, which does not affect their study. The most important aspects of this phenomenon, namely “dysphemic pragmatics – causes of origin, socio-historical and psychological distribution, lead to the fact that they remain unexplored” [Rezanova, 2008:3]. In the view of scholar L.V Kvaskova, “a detailed study of linguistic and functional nature of negative-looking words to counter their origins in oral speech” [Kvaskova, 2016:353].

To interpret the term “dysphemism”, we refer to lexicographic sources:

The dictionary edited by V.N.Yarseva comments on dysphemism: “replacing an emotionally and stylistically neutral word with rude, unkind words” [Yarseva, 1998:590].

T.V.Matveeva gives an extended definition of dysphemism in her paper: dysphemism is “the rough reporting of an emotional state, the replacement of a stylistically neutral word or phrase with a rough word, or phrase”. In the process of communication, the speaker aims to humiliate, insult, discredit his interlocutor. Meanwhile, the rules of speech are violated, impudence is observed in relationships [Matveeva, 2010:95].

From these definitions it can be said that for every dysphemism there is a stylistically neutral synonym for it. However, the scientist L.V. Porokhniskaya notes in her paper that this neutral word cannot always be circumscribed from euphemism, dysphemism, orthophemism [Porokhniskaya, 2013:143].

Scientist N. Abakova, who researched dysphemism in the field of politics, concludes that dysphemization can be understood as a tactical language tool that can be used to achieve the desired pragmatic effect and purposefully influence the audience [Abakova, 2013:27].

Scientist A.N. Rezanova, by dysphemism, understands the use of neutral lexicon that represents, or has a negative assessment of, forms of taboo language that are inappropriate for a speech situation with a purpose, as well as for solving a communicative task [Rezanova, 2008:8].

Scientist notes the preservation of denotate as a characteristic sign of dysphemia, with the change occurring only in the connotative component. In this regard, let us consider the example of the linguistic scientist L.Mosievich: *С. Берлускони в разговоре об избранном президенте США Обаме пошутил насчет его “загорелости”, что было намеком на цвет кожи афроамериканца.* – (In a conversation about elected president of the U.S.–Obama, S.Berlusconi joked about the president’s “sunburn”, hinting at African American’s skin color.) In this case, the connotative neutral sign (загорелость–sunburn) acquires a negative meaning in context and belongs to the group of dysphemisms [Mosievich, 2009:359].

Dysphemia is a discursive phenomenon, while dysphemism is both a language (replacing one lexical unit with another) and a speech phenomenon (a means of substitution to perform some communicative task).

The phenomenon of dysphemia has not been studied as deeply as euphemia, nor has this concept been a separate object of study in French

linguistics. When we turned to the etymology of the concept of "dysphemism" in French, we looked at this information:

La notion du XXe siècle, construit sur le modèle de euphémisme par substitution du préfixe dys- au préfixe eu-. Mot de formation savante forgé à partir du grec ancien δυσφημισμός, dysphêmos ("emploi d'un mot défavorable"), composé de δυσ, dys ("difficile, mauvais, négatif") et de φήμη, phêmê ("parole") [site].

It is a term related to the 20th century, consisting of two ancient Greek content – "dys" – "difficult, bad, negative", "phêmi" – "I speak". Inversely to euphemism, it means "bad speech".

The Spanish linguist da Silva Correa names the concept of dysphemism as "cacofemismo", "contra-eufemismo", "anti-eufemismo" [da Silva Correa, 1927 : 445-787]. Linguistic scholar Grant, on the other hand, describes dysphemism in itself as "mot fort" – "strong words" or "malphemism" – "bad utterance", a combination of all evil vices, including rudeness, hatred, ridicule, blasphemy, etc. [Grant, 1977:246-253].

Therefore, dysphemism does not take a single form, except for etiquette, it is not limited to vulgar, obscene words. That is, it would be wrong to view dysphemism as a product of coarse, vulgar speech, words and phrases expressing unpleasantness. It is desirable to define dysphemism through the context (text). For example, taking a word as a strictly dysphemic word, may not justify itself in all contextual situations:

1. *Dans de nombreuses propriétés, les bêtes commencent à mourir en raison du manque d'eau* [Le Monde (2002). – (Animals are dying due to water shortages in many places.)

2. *Et voyez maintenant comme elle aime les bêtes!* [Alphonse de Lamartine (1790-1869)] – (Now you see how she loves animals.)

3. *Elle n'est pas bête, elle est loin d'être bête.* – (He is not stupid, he is far from stupidity.)

4. *"Quelle bête es-tu?"* – ("How stupid?")

5. *"Elle aime toujours chercher la petite bête dans mon travail!"* – ("He always likes to find fault in my work!")

6. *Cette femme est sa bête noire!* – (He hates this woman!)

7. *Elle a un caractère de cochon.* (avoir un sale caractère) – (Her character is pig-like.)

In the examples above, it can be observed that the same word acquires a different meaning in different contexts, the dysphemism meaning is determined by the state of the text.

Thus, the main task of dysphemism is to draw attention to something unpleasant or an unpleasant event, dysphemism - using stylistically negative coloring or neutral words in order to deliberately humiliate the interlocutor, discredit them or express such a relationship as of dissatisfaction, disdain, hatred in a specific situation.

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